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Review Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Cough Syrup

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ABSTRACT

The cough is one of the most common problems faced all people. There are mainly two type of cough, one is Dry cough and another one wet cough. Dry cough is no mucous secretion while in wet cough there is cough with mucous secretion. Syrup is commonly used and popular dosage form which is used to cure cough and cold, because it having easy to patient compliance. The herbal cough syrup was formulated using crude drugs as Marshmallow root (as a anti-irritant), Elderberry (as a anti-bacterial), Pineapple (as a anti-inflammatory) & Ivy (as a anti-viral). Quality of herbal cough syrup was evaluated for pre-formulation and post formulation like density, viscosity, pH and various organoleptic characteristic.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal cough syrup is defined as decoction with honey or sugar. Herbal cough syrup is formulated using crude drugs as Vasaka, Marshmallow, Elderberry, Cinnamon & Thyme etc. Herbal cough syrup is used in both dry & wet cough. The cough syrup medication is a liquid dosage form use of oral liquid pharmaceutical has been confirm on basic ease of administration to those people to have the problem in swallowing of solid dosage form of medication. Syrup is a concentrated solution contains sugar/honey and purified water. When syrup without a medication but the flavouring agent present are known as flavoured

syrup or non-medicated syrup. Flavoured syrup are frequently used as a vehicle for unpleasant test of medication results is medicated syrups. Syrup is very prominent delivery vehicle use for the anti-tussive medication because they give a more soothing to swallow then the table and capsule.

Literature Review: -

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5. Kraft (1999) Noted That The High Mucilage Content Creates A Protective Layer Over Irritated Mucosa, Particularly Effective In Cases Of Dry Cough And Pharyngitis. Clinical Data Suggest Symptom Relief Within Days Of Marshmallow Based Syrup Use.

Classification of Cough: -

- Acute cough – Not more than 3 weeks duration.
- Chronic cough –More than 3 weeks.
- Dry cough – No mucous secretion
- Wet cough – With mucous secretion.

ADVANTAGE

- Provide protection from allergic cough.
- Easily available.
- Lower cost.
- Good patient compliance.
- Herbs grow in common places.
- Not required prescription

- No side effects

DISADVANTAGES: -

- No proper regulations.
- Herbs interact with modern medicines.
- Lack of dosage instruction.
- Delayed onset of action.

Aim And Objective:

Aim: Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Cough Syrup.

Objective Of the Study:

1. soothing throat irritation
2. reducing inflammation
3. natural remedy for respiratory issues
4. relieving cough symptoms

Plan Of Work:

The present proposed research work is planned as follows:

1	Literature review
2	Abstract
3	Introduction
4	Material (Ingredients)
5	Method Of Preparation
6	Evaluation
7	Discussion and Conclusion
8	References

Formulation Table: -

Ingredients	Quantity Taken (For 100ML)
Marshmallow Root	2gm
Elecampane Root	3gm
Ivy Leaf	1 gm
Elderberry	2gm
Vasaka	3gm
Pineapple	8gm

Cinnamon	2gm
Thyme	2gm
Honey	45%

Method Of Preparation of Herbal Cough Syrup: -

➤ Preparation of Extract by Decoction method: -

Weigh accurately each ingredient except honey. Ingredients are mixed using 500ml water in round bottom flask. Attach to the reflux condenser and mixed material was boiled under carefully by using water bath for 3 hrs. Boil until total volume become one fourth part of solution. Then liquid extract was cooled and filtered.

Preparation final cough syrup:-

To prepare final cough syrup 45% of honey was mixed slowly side by side continuous stirring in

decoction solution. Herbal cough syrup was prepared and used for cough.

Figure: 13

Figure: 14

EVALUATION OF HERBAL COUGH SYRUP:-

Test	Procedure
Colour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 5 ml of prepared syrup was taken on a watch glass ▪ Watch glass placed against white background in white tube light. ▪ Colour was observed by naked eyes
Odour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2ml of prepared syrup was taken & smelled by individually. ▪ Time interval between 2 smelling was 2 minutes to nullify effect of previous smelling.
Taste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A pinch of final syrup was taken and examined on taste buds of the tongue.
pH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 10 ml of prepared syrup taken in 100 ml of volumetric flask. ▪ Make up volume to 100 ml with dist. water. ▪ Sonicated for 10 minutes. ▪ pH was measured by using digital pH meter.
Viscosity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The viscosity of formulation was determined by using Ostwald's U-tube viscometer.
Density	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Density of formulation was determined by using density bottle.

Table: 02

EVALUATION TABLE:-

Test	Observed
Colour	Yellowish brown
Odour	Aromatic
Taste	Sweet
pH	7
Viscosity	4.96 cp
Density	1.17g/ml

Table: 03

Yellowish-brown

Figure: 15

pH= 7

Figure: 16

DISCUSSION: -Herbs have been an important source to improve the quality of human life for thousands of years. In fact 25% of all medical prescriptions are based on substances derived from plants or plant-derived synthetic analogues. It has been estimated by World Health Organization (WHO) that approximately 80% of world's population, mainly residing in developing countries, still depends on the complementary and

alternative systems of medicine, while about half of the population in industrialized countries use herbal medicines. This syrup consists of Marshmallow, Elderberry, Elecampane root, Vasaka, Cinnamon, Ivy leaf. Vasaka is commonly used to treat chronic bronchitis, asthma and cough. Pineapple and cinnamon are used to thin the mucus. Marshmallow is used to reduce irritation. Ivy is used as anti-viral.

CONCLUSION: - The preformulation studies of all these formulation were within specifications. Also the physiochemical properties of prepared syrup like colour, odour, taste, pH, viscosity, density were satisfactory but among the formulation was within the all specification, it has proper concentration of honey as per IP and also a good preservative. Herbal product is high demand because of the least possibilities of side effect. The percent study help to develop effective and safe herbal cough with 45% w/v honey as a base of cough syrup. Elderberry is used as anti-bacterial.

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